

Venture fund as an institution of venture capital accumulation

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Abstract: This article reveals the venture capital fund as a subject of venture capital investment, which are pooled investment funds that manage investors' money seeking private stakes in start-ups, small, medium-sized enterprises with strong growth potential. These investments are generally characterised as very high risk and high return opportunities, hence legal objectives and economic objectives should be pursued while accumulating and raising venture capital.

Keywords: venture capital fund, venture capital, management company, portfolio companies, startup.

Introduction

In a modern innovation-based economy, venture capital plays a key role in financing and developing promising startups and high-tech companies. The most important institutional mechanism that ensures the accumulation and efficient allocation of venture capital is the venture capital fund. These specialised financial institutions act as intermediaries between investors seeking to invest in high-risk but potentially high-return projects and entrepreneurs in need of capital to implement innovative ideas.

A venture fund is a unique form of organising the investment process, combining the financial resources of various categories of investors - from wealthy individuals to large institutional investors such as pension funds, insurance companies and endowments. Due to their structure and mechanisms of functioning, venture funds are able not only to accumulate significant financial resources, but also to apply a professional approach to the

selection, evaluation and support of investment projects, which significantly increases the probability of successful implementation of innovations.

In the conditions of global competition and acceleration of technological progress, the study of venture capital funds as institutions of venture capital accumulation becomes especially relevant. Understanding the principles of formation and functioning of venture capital funds, their role in the innovation ecosystem and their impact on economic development allows us to identify the key success factors of innovative entrepreneurship and identify promising areas for improving innovation financing mechanisms.

Materials and Methods of Research

In the past, venture capital investments were only available to professional venture capitalists, but now, accredited investors have more opportunities to participate in venture capital investments. Even so, venture capital funds remain inaccessible to ordinary investors.

The participants in a venture capital fund are the investors who put money into the fund and the management company, a venture capital firm that makes investment decisions and handles the assets [1].

When structuring a venture capital fund, attention is paid to the requirements for structuring the fund and the fund's transactions by investors and/or to investors, also the fund at the initial stage of formation may face problems in the field of civil law and taxation.

When structuring a venture capital fund, the management company or a participant in the fund pursues the following main objectives:

I. Limitation of liability - investors are limited partners and one of the objectives is to limit their liability for the fate of the fund's activities based on their share of the investment in the fund.

II. Avoiding double taxation and ensuring minimum taxation of fund management fees - in the first case, double taxation may be in the form of income received

by the fund in the form of dividends or interest from portfolio companies, or at the time of withdrawal from the investment in capital gains; or in the investors' realisation of their investment in the fund. As we pointed out in the previous paragraph, when an investor invests his or her capital in the fund, the investor must be sure that he or she gains something, compared to an investor funding on his or her own. In the second, minimising the fund management fee in value added tax.

III. Optimality and suitability for any investors - the purpose of the fund is to create a unified system of activity, convenient for any investors, so that both the latter and the former are not subject to double taxation, are exempt from taxes of insurance companies, pension funds, and other legal and natural persons of any jurisdiction.

IV. Offer of participation in the fund to appropriate investors - in carrying out their activities, funds are mainly specialised in a particular area, for example, environmental, therefore, it allows the fund to target specific investors.

V. Ease of management - the legal form should be easy to manage in order to facilitate the fulfilment of the above objectives, in case of incompatibility, the fund is faced with two choices: the legal form or the satisfaction of the objectives [2].

Research Results

Previously stated, a fund is a pool of money managed by an independent management company owned by the financial institution or its managers. Depending on its structure, the fund is owned by investors who own shares, interests or units in the fund. Funds mobilised from investors are invested by the fund in portfolio companies.

The management company is usually registered in the form of a limited liability partnership [3]. In its activity, the management company receives a fund management fee of 2% (another % can also be set) and uses it to pay the resulting costs associated with the activities of the firm: rent, employee salaries, etc. [4]. The form of a limited liability partnership is used in most private equity and venture capital funds, its participants are liable for obligations for an amount not exceeding their income.

The Management Company consists of the General Partner (GP) and the Limited Partner (LP). The General Partner has a fiduciary responsibility to the Limited Partners. His task is to attract and manage venture capital funds with the right to act by proxy on behalf of the limited partners, to make investment decisions, and to assist in the exit of the company from its portfolio (startup) Often acts as a management company of private equity and venture capital funds [5].

Limited partners - an investor in a limited partnership, who does not participate in the management of the partnership, has limited liability in relation to the debts and obligations of the latter, acts as a passive investor. Act mainly as institutional investors, such as pension funds, insurance companies, endowments, etc [4].

As for portfolio companies, we mean startups that have presented their projects and received investments from the venture fund in exchange for shares - preferred shares [6]. At the same time, the fund can withdraw its profits through mergers and acquisitions or IPOs, and then convert them into cash.

In carrying on their business, venture capital fund participants enter into a limited partnership agreement, a limited partnership, which is a contractual arrangement between a GP and an LP in which one partner assumes full liability in return for full control of the partnership. Its difference from a regular partnership is the limited liability of the partners. However, profits are distributed pro rata, or as specified in the contract. Fund contracts are usually for 10 years with an option to extend for 3 years. During this period, management companies attract investments and rationally invest in innovative projects, which they consider promising, taking into account the risks and time of project realisation and return of the invested funds with interest. Fund managers themselves directly receive remuneration in the form of a management fee in the amount of 1-2% (of the capital invested in the fund) and 20% commission for the result (received profit for the invested funds) [7].

In general, during the implementation of its activities venture capital funds conclude

various agreements with partners, investors, innovators and other persons, to the main ones we can include a limited partnership agreement - Limited Partnership Agreement - regulates the relationship between the managing partner and investors, as we have indicated above, an agreement on the provision of investment services - Investment Management Agreement - an agreement between the fund and the management company, an accession agreement - Subscription Document - this document is designed to join the investor to the LPA, thus, the LPA can be considered as an agreement between the fund and the management company.

The contracting process is important because contracts are the basis of the understanding and relationship between the business firm and the fund manager.

Contracts that are typically presented and negotiated during the investment process include: term sheet, shareholder agreement and subscription agreement [7].

The term sheet sets out the intended terms of the deal, while they do not act as binding contracts, they are intended to establish areas of agreement before lawyers for both parties draft a binding agreement. The use of a term sheet not only allows the entrepreneur to have a clear idea of what the final terms will be so that the parties can continue to negotiate, but more importantly it in turn saves costs for the parties as the basic terms are assumed to be acceptable to both parties, hence this results in fewer billable hours spent reviewing contracts.

In contrast, a shareholders' agreement is a legally binding contract between the shareholders of a company that sets out the 'new' terms of the relationship between the shareholders with the inclusion of the venture capital shareholder.

A subscription agreement is interpreted as an agreement between a venture capital shareholder and a company. This agreement sets out the terms of the subscription: shareholders subscribe for shares and the subscription agreement defines the type of shares, the rights resulting from ownership and the terms of payment. The terms of these contracts are usually included in the memorandum and articles of association of the

entrepreneurial firm.

The terms of the contract typically include cash flow (payments to the entrepreneur and investors) and control rights (decision-making rights) [8].

Based on US-only datasets, the experts show that venture capitalists separately allocate cash flow rights, voting rights, board rights, liquidation rights, and other control rights. They find that convertible preferred equity is typically used and that cash flow rights, voting rights, control rights, and future financial results are often dependent on observable financial and non-financial metrics. In addition, venture capitalists often include provisions to mitigate potential delay between the entrepreneur and the investor, and, the former retain control over the management of the firm if the firm performs poorly. Once the firm's performance improves, entrepreneurs regain control as well as additional rights to cash flow [10].

There is a relationship to be found in firm choice and capital structure and in order to find and understand it, it will be useful to consider the properties of different types of securities.

Common equity is similar to a call option. Holders of common equity have the right to claim all of the firm's cash flows, but only after all other claimants have been satisfied.

If the firm goes bankrupt, shareholders are the last to be paid (debt holders have priority over preferred shareholders, who in turn have priority over common shareholders); however, common shareholders cannot lose more than their investment in the firm because of the firm's limited liability.

Common equity is thus analogous to a call option on a firm, whereby exercise of the option requires liquidation of the firm and repayment of the face value of the debt (the option price). The payout function of common equity is limited and lower in terms of the value of the investment in common stock and unlimited upside potential. In contrast, the payoff on direct (non-convertible) debt is limited to the present discounted value of all interest payments and principal (similarly, the payoff on non-convertible preferred equity

is limited to the present discounted value of all pre-determined preferred dividends). If the entrepreneurial firm fails to pay interest on the debt, the investor can force the firm into bankruptcy. If the entrepreneurial firm fails to pay pre-determined preferred dividends, the investor cannot force the firm into bankruptcy, but all preferred dividends must be paid before any general dividends are paid.

Venture capitalists typically invest in entrepreneurial firms for two to seven years prior to exit. There are two main exit paths for successful entrepreneurial firms backed by venture capitalists:

1. IPO
2. Acquisition (PR: stakes).

There are other exit routes, these can be buyback of shares by the entrepreneur from the venture capitalist, or secondary sales where the venture capitalist sells the shares to another investor while the entrepreneur retains the latter, or write-offs - however, with these exit routes, the returns are lower.

The venture capitalist's pre-planned exit strategy need not necessarily be disclosed to the entrepreneur at the time of investment, but it may be disclosed to show his intention to develop the firm to its full potential.

A pre-planned exit is not part of the contract. However, the main reason why a planned exit affects the contract is that at the time of the actual exit, venture capitalists are the financial intermediaries between the entrepreneurial firm and the new owners (public shareholders if an IPO or the acquiring firm if an acquisition).

Conclusions

It is theoretically natural to expect that the distribution of control and decision-making rights between investor and entrepreneur will depend on a pre-planned IPO versus a pre-planned acquisition. Contractual governance between the private investor and the entrepreneur exists in a number of aspects, including security design, veto rights and control (e.g. the right to replace the founding entrepreneur as CEO, co-sale agreements and

veto rights on asset sales/purchases, changes in control and share issuance) [7].

In practice, there are two possible ways in which pre-planned exit strategies can affect contract formation.

I. A situation in which the venture capitalist forms a pre-planned exit strategy but does not disclose it (or does not fully disclose it) to the startup during contract negotiation. The incentive for the venture capitalist not to disclose is the fact that the entrepreneur is effectively forced out of the firm as CEO when exiting by acquisition (of a stake). Therefore, most startups are reluctant to agree to exit in an acquisition. Consequently, this may lead to venture capitalists who plan to exit by acquiring a stake to negotiate stronger control rights to force the innovator firm to agree to the acquisition.

II. A situation where the venture capitalist plans the exit route in advance and informs the entrepreneur of this strategy, then the latter may reasonably agree to cede control rights to the venture capitalist in order to facilitate the exit from the acquisition, thereby increasing the sale price of the entrepreneurial firm. Thus, the venture capitalist and the entrepreneur rationally agree to cede control rights to the venture capitalist in the initial agreement in order to maximise the expected value of the firm at the time of the actual exit. However, if the entrepreneur is unwilling to relinquish control rights to the venture capitalist because of the loss of the entrepreneur's private benefits, it is much less likely that the firm will receive financing [7].

As for the contracts themselves, they will vary depending on the quality of the laws in the country. On the one hand, contracts can substitute for poor legal protection, so more detailed contracts may be found in countries with a lower quality of law.

On the other hand, the quality of the law may make it easier to enforce contracts and lead to more detailed contracts, both for the national law as well as to serve as a model for the law of other countries.

Having studied the agreements side, let us conclude by looking at the life of a fund in general.

As a rule, a venture capital fund operates for a certain period of time - 8-10 years. This term is necessarily indicated in the Limited Partnership Agreement and at the end of this term the fund must be liquidated and all liquid assets distributed among investors.

However, it should be noted that the fund may be extended by the managing partner, but this action requires the consent of the advisory board or the consent of a majority of the limited partner investors.

In this case, extending the fund's term is not preferable for investors, but, on the other hand, extending the fund's term may be beneficial for participants, especially investors themselves, as the extension will allow them to realize illiquid assets of the fund at a more favourable price.

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